

Will carbon management take off in Europe? How to get both industry and society on board?

Insights from an analysis of the European Commission's Industrial Carbon Management Strategy Call for Evidence submissions

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Intended audience: EU/Member Countries' decision-makers on carbon management.

This policy brief is based on the scientific paper "*An analysis of the European Industrial Carbon Management Strategy consultation: Who makes the normative decisions?*" by Senni Määttä et al and insights from the "Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions - Towards an ambitious Industrial Carbon Management for the EU" (Industrial Carbon Management Strategy) published on February 6, 2024.

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Executive Summary

In their analysis of the stakeholder submissions to the Industrial Carbon Management call for evidence, Määttä et al. find **two distinct views** that stakeholders tend to adopt: a **market-driven approach**, emphasising economic considerations, and a **society-driven approach**, prioritising societal and environmental concerns. Advocates of the market-driven approach are concerned that too strict regulations can hinder the emerging market, while advocates of the society-driven approach are concerned that without cautious regulation, carbon management will not lead to the desired climate benefits. At first glance, focusing on economic considerations appears to be the best strategy to foster the business case for carbon management, but **focusing only on economic considerations may not bring about the needed predictability for carbon management deployment**. Providing full predictability is impossible as the development of carbon management implementation is interlinked with the development in other decarbonisation areas such as hydrogen and renewable energy. Still, **predictability plays a crucial role in carbon management deployment, and regulation is necessary to provide long-term and predictable policy support** for these applications. The market-driven approach's resistance to regulation is at odds with the goal of providing a sufficient level of predictability. Therefore, a combination of the two approaches is recommended.

1 Background

In the pursuit of climate mitigation within Europe, the implementation of an industrial carbon management strategy marks a significant milestone. Mr Daniels from Global CCS Institute commented on the strategy saying "Setting clear targets is a crucial step to ensure predictability and further drive investment in those climate technologies that will be needed to reach Europe's ambitious climate goals" (The Global CCS Institute, 2024), thus emphasising the link between the official strategy and the core focus of this policy brief on the stakeholder perspectives and their implications related to CCUS implementation.

The industry call for a business case and a predictable policy and support framework for carbon management is loud and clear. Presently, industries face a landscape of uncertainty, lacking sufficient support not only in terms of funding but also in navigating through complex procedural requirements such as permitting, amidst an unpredictable political framework. The willingness to adopt carbon management and decarbonise is high, but the current environment of uncertainty and lack of economic viability results in a deadlock, where many companies come to the conclusion that the best course of action is to wait until greater certainty is achieved. This situation underscores the critical need for a clearer, more actionable framework so that the ambitious goals for carbon management are achievable.

Stakeholders advocate for enabling the market while raising concerns that any restrictions on CCUS implementation could be a barrier to market development. At the same time, they call for clarity and

predictability, noting the detrimental effects of ambiguity which can lead to inaction. These statements are at odds as regulation is key to providing a level of predictability. A key example of a market-driven approach to decarbonisation includes the EU Emissions Trading System, which has included volatile prices and a significant level of uncertainty. Moreover, market-driven approaches are unlikely to achieve a fair and inclusive transition (Rycroft et al., 2023), which is a key consideration for CCUS deployment in Europe, where current development focuses on North and West Europe, while East and South Europe is at risk of being left behind. Policy-driven deployment allows for a greater level of predictability and harmonization (Rycroft et al., 2023). While pursuing predictability, it is important to acknowledge that some level of uncertainty is inevitable.

The EU's definition of Carbon Management, encompassing Carbon Capture and Storage, Carbon Capture and Utilisation as well as Carbon Removal, serves as a cornerstone for the European Commission's strategies moving forward. To develop the next steps after the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy (European Commission, 2024), policymakers face the challenge of reconciling diverse views, perspectives, interests, and carbon management pathways. Carbon management is a collaborative challenge, including collaboration across the value chain and borders. Developing CO₂ infrastructure will be costly, and many projects have faced public resistance, emphasizing the crucial role of societal support. To ensure that Carbon Management implementation reaches its goals, a balanced approach that integrates economic considerations with societal goals and fosters collaboration is paramount.

The collaborative dimension of Carbon management underpins the evolving business models necessitating cross-sectorial and cross-border partnerships, particularly related to CO₂ transport and storage across the value chain. Due to high costs (see Box#1 "*Industrial Carbon Management Strategy in numbers*") and the need for interoperability, in fact, the transport and infrastructure must be shared. Achieving effective collaboration should not be assumed, and various criteria for this, such as trust, shared understanding of the 'mission' and effective coordination, have been proposed in academic literature (Ansell, 2007; Ansell et al., 2017; Douglas & Ansell, 2021; Siddiki et al., 2017).

The Industrial Carbon Management Strategy outlines ambitious goals for implementing European carbon management and contributes to the growing momentum in this area. The European Carbon Management community, reflecting a collective eagerness amongst stakeholders, demonstrates a strong willingness and enthusiasm to implement carbon management technologies rapidly in order to achieve net zero emissions.

However, the strategy reveals a challenge, keeping the regulatory and policy framework predictable while carbon management keeps evolving (especially as it is linked with other clean energy moves, like hydrogen and renewable power). The decarbonisation of industries, for example, relies on a combination of solutions like CCUS, electrification, hydrogen, and energy efficiency and requires access to affordable clean energy. Recognizing the types of Carbon Management applications that align with Europe's broader decarbonization goals and providing steadfast policy support for these selected avenues, emerge as critical steps.

Box#1: Industrial Carbon Management Strategy in numbers

- Need to develop at least 50 Mtpa of CO₂ storage capacity by 2030 and reach CO₂ injection capacity of at least 250 million tonnes per year by 2040 - *Net-Zero Industry Act*
- Capturing approximately 280 Mtpa of CO₂ by 2040 and around 450 Mtpa of CO₂ by 2050 is necessary to meet the intermediate EU 2040 climate target and reaching climate neutrality by 2050 - *European Commission's assessment*
- Transport network could span up to 7,300 km in 2030 and 19,000 km by 2040, costing €12.2 billion and €16 billion by 2030 and 2040 respectively

Stakeholder views indicate two approaches to carbon management: market-driven and society-driven. These approaches show two perspectives on the challenge of predictability, societal and environmental considerations and financial incentivization.

2 Two approaches to Carbon Management

Based on the stakeholder submissions to the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy call for evidence, Määttä et al. study identified two approaches to Carbon Management, a market-driven approach and a society-driven approach. These approaches are best understood as a spectrum, with many stakeholder views placed somewhere in between the two approaches.

A Market-driven approach

A market-driven approach tends to see regulation as a risk to technology deployment, opting for a free market. It argues that now is not the time for extensive regulation on carbon management as this can work as a barrier to the emerging market. The market-driven approach reasons with carbon management as the end goal in mind.

A Society-driven approach

The society-driven approach generally sees regulation as a necessary condition to make sure that the technology leads to desired results, opting for a more controlled approach. The society-driven approach tends to reason with climate change mitigation as the end goal, and carbon management as one of several pathways to achieve this goal.

Market-driven approaches are found to foster innovation and be cost-effective (Sacchi et al., 2014; Sonneborn, 2004). The advocates for a market-driven approach to Carbon Management believe that focusing on economic incentives can significantly speed up the adoption of Carbon Management. This belief is underlined by the idea that investment in the CCUS value chain will not only foster more investment but also enable a scale-up in both the quantity and size of installations. Such expansion, coupled with ensuring a learning effect, will have a significant role in the acceleration of Carbon Management technology deployment. However, it is crucial that this pursuit of acceleration does not come with blinders on. In particular, the presence of clear legal frameworks and the certainty of regulatory constraints are also seen as key drivers of investment. Investors are more likely to commit to the CCUS value chain when there is clarity in legal and regulatory expectations, underscoring that a balanced approach, which includes both market incentives and regulatory certainty, is essential for successful Carbon Management deployment. Focusing only on economic considerations can result in a slower pace and decreased depth of change instead of the aspired acceleration (Adler, 2022; Chaudhary, 2022). Moreover, market-driven approaches resist regulation, but at the same time, effective collaboration as well as making long-term business decisions requires clear rules.

Moreover, collaboration requires trust, and carbon management implementation requires trust between industry, governments, and societal actors (Porter et al., 2022). Industry requires a business case and a fair

competitive environment to be able to implement Carbon Management technologies. This relies on the existence of a supporting policy environment. Effective policy requires societal support, which in turn relies on societal trust. Societal trust cannot be achieved without clear rules and transparency on carbon management practices. In this context, the European Commission's Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), which is currently in the final stages of Trilogue negotiations, emerges as a critical instrument. By introducing essential standardisation to the monitoring and reporting of carbon removals within the EU, the CRCF aims to support deployment. This standardization is not just a regulatory milestone but a significant step towards building the necessary trust by making carbon management efforts more transparent, measurable, and verifiable across the board.

The existing critique towards Carbon Management has been largely based on the question of whether all applications of Carbon Management technologies result in climate benefit (e.g. Climate Action Tracker, 2023). The society-driven approach focuses on this question, and the advocates of this approach argue that carbon management technologies should be implemented only in cases where no other feasible decarbonisation solutions exist. They see regulation as a necessary step to ensure that Carbon Management technology implementation does not result in applications where the climate benefit is not clear (see Strategy's climate targets in Box#1, "Industrial Carbon Management Strategy in numbers"). This provides clear rules and transparency for carbon management development.

The society-driven approach calls for clear decisions on the types of Carbon Management applications that should be pursued and supported. Some public responses to the published Industrial Carbon Management Strategy argued that the Strategy failed to make these tough decisions.

"The European Commission's Industrial Carbon Management Strategy only delays the inevitable, as the discussion on where and under what conditions carbon capture is deemed (politically) acceptable will have to be picked up by the next Commission." (Cătuți & Vangenechten, 2024)

Regardless of the approach, the EU is aiming to create a unified market for industrial carbon management that is crucial for leveraging economies of scale and preparing for future infrastructure needs, ensuring that we avoid piecemeal or inadequate infrastructure solutions. Central to establishing this single market is the development of essential infrastructure, particularly for transport, which remains a time-intensive necessity, irrespective of whether a market-driven or society-driven approach is pursued. This underscores the pivotal role of "regulation" (see Box#2, "Drivers for effective carbon management regulations") in shaping the framework within which these approaches operate and the infrastructure is developed, setting the stage for a more detailed discussion on its impact and implications.

Box#2: Drivers for effective carbon management regulations

- Establish a framework encouraging responsible operation and investment; risks and liabilities
- Balance stability and predictability with flexibility and adaptability to new scientific information; and
- Provide ease of implementation for both regulators and industry.

Still, we recommend that a careful balance is required between the market-driven and society-driven approaches.

3 Providing clarity without imposing regulatory barriers?

The message that Carbon Management implementation requires clarity and a comprehensive policy framework was clear in the call for evidence submissions. Clear rules and mutual understanding are also the foundation of effective collaboration (Ansell, 2007; Määttä, 2021). This call for clarity conflicts with the call for limited restrictions. Restrictions and regulation, while seemingly paradoxical, are essential in furnishing the clarity needed for Carbon Management implementation to flourish.

However, the capacity to provide complete clarity is inherently constrained. The trajectory of the Carbon Management implementation is strictly linked to developments such as renewable energy, and hydrogen deployment, due to their complimentary roles and interdependency. Inherent uncertainty is unavoidable as the future of these interconnected fields is unpredictable. Despite this, incorporating elements of a society-driven approach and making tough decisions about the specific Carbon Management strategies to be pursued in Europe, can significantly reduce this uncertainty. It is crucial to understand that these choices need to be in harmony with decisions made in other related sectors. For example, the ambition to scale up CCUS technologies relies on the availability of sufficient clean and affordable energy to power these processes.

Some of the European Commission's recent developments already indicate a balancing of a market-driven and society-driven approaches. Central to the discussion of policy clarity is the need for clear guidelines around rights of access to infrastructure, ownership issues, and the setting of tariffs. These aspects are particularly critical for emitters and project developers who navigate the complex landscape of Carbon Management. Clear policies in these areas are vital to alleviate investment risks and to sustain the development of the necessary infrastructure. The European Commission acknowledges this need and is planning to prepare a CO₂ transport/infrastructure regulatory package to address these concerns, thus smoothing out the path for investment.

In conclusion, while the challenge of balancing clarity with the need for flexibility and minimal restrictions is non-trivial, it is an essential task. The European Commission's efforts to refine the regulatory landscape for CO₂ transport and infrastructure development underscore a commitment to this balance. By providing clear guidelines on access, ownership, and tariffs, and ensuring that Carbon Management decisions are synchronized with broader energy and decarbonization strategies, Europe can navigate the uncertainties of the future with greater confidence and purpose, moving closer to its net-zero emissions goal.

4 What if the market-based approach becomes dominant?

The existing EU policy framework for Carbon Management leaves room for multiple different Carbon Management pathways with the climate benefits of some being less clear than others. The impact of Carbon Management applications relies on the availability of clean energy to power the processes and a full lifecycle assessment. Truly sustainable adoption relies on a wide range of factors, including social, environmental and economic considerations (Covarrubias, Kustova, de Gooyert, & de Coninck, 2024; Covarrubias, Kustova, de Gooyert, Nipius, et al., 2024; Hardisty et al., 2011).

De Kleijne et al. (2022) have shown that by 2050, only those products that either store CO₂ permanently or are produced using only zero-emissions energy sources can align with the Paris Agreement goals. Focusing only on economic considerations at the expense of the ultimate goal of climate change mitigation may result in lock-in by CCU technologies with limited emissions reduction. Economic incentives alone might support CCU applications that do not align with eco-efficiency principles, as long as they appear cost-effective.

An example that underscores the potential pitfalls of prioritizing economic considerations is Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR). While not widely adopted in Europe, EOR exemplifies the type of pathways that are pursued if the focus is on economic considerations alone, directly contradicting the objectives of fossil fuel phase-out.

To ensure Carbon Management efforts yield the intended climate benefits and push innovation while providing economic incentives, a combination of market- and society-driven approaches is necessary. Current debates and initiatives steer towards a market-driven approach, raising concerns about a potentially narrow focus where societal factors are overlooked, the role of Carbon Management in the broader decarbonization agenda is evaluated purely on profitability, and collaborative efforts are compromised.

Integrating societal considerations ensures that Carbon Management technologies are developed and deployed in a way that supports the EU's climate goals comprehensively, avoiding prioritising short-term economic gains. This balanced approach we are stressing encourages innovation, enhances clarity, and fosters effective collaboration, ensuring that Carbon Management contributes significantly to Europe's journey towards net-zero emissions.

Box#3: Key societal considerations (adapted from Covarrubias, Kustova, de Gooyert, & de Coninck, 2024)

- Currently, CCS is primarily employed in capturing CO₂ during natural gas processing and also finds application in enhanced oil recovery. However, these practices are widely viewed as incompatible with the Paris Agreement and EU decarbonization goals.
- CCS is often regarded as a temporary fix that addresses symptoms, potentially perpetuating the use of fossil fuels. This perception can divert attention from more systemic solutions, reinforcing carbon lock-in and overshadowing alternative mitigation technologies.
- While CCS may offer a short-term means to reduce CO₂ emissions, it is not a sustainable long-term solution. There is a pressing need for more effective and sustainable climate-neutral alternatives.
- When CCS is utilized as Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) to offset residual emissions for achieving Net-Zero and to compensate for surpassing the carbon budget, CCS coupled with biomass faces criticism due to its reliance on significant amounts of sustainable biomass.
- Concerns about the perceived risks associated with CO₂ leakage during long-distance transport and geological storage raise safety apprehensions and fears of re-emission.

5 Recommendations

1. **Despite industry calling for limited restrictions to carbon management, we suggest to policymakers that the industry could accept more stringent regulations if the policy and regulatory framework is predictable.** Currently, high uncertainty on issues such as whether all CCU applications are supported results in waiting. While companies wait for greater certainty, the needed actions get delayed more and more.
2. **Single market:** to foster a robust single market for Carbon Management, the EC must ensure transparent collaboration in CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure (atlas of potential CO₂ storage site and CO₂ transport/infrastructure regulatory package). A balanced strategy is crucial, merging economic incentives with decarbonization, social, and environmental goals to prevent lock-in scenarios and support viable carbon management solutions aligned with climate objectives. Recognizing carbon management as waste management highlights the need for government backing. Essential to this is harmonizing EU funds, national subsidies, and private investments through coordinated policy efforts, fostering a market conducive to sustainable and strategic growth.
3. **Interconnected Decision-making:** Recognize the interconnected nature of Carbon Management with other areas such as renewable energy, hydrogen, and energy efficiency, which are all interconnected solutions to industrial decarbonisation. Ensure that decisions in Carbon Management are aligned with decisions in these interconnected areas to maximize effectiveness and minimize uncertainty.
4. **Long-term Climate Benefit:** Prioritize Carbon Management pathways that offer clear climate benefits, address societal concerns, and are compatible with long-term climate goals, such as products storing CO₂ permanently or produced from zero-emissions energy sources.
5. **Streamlining permitting processes is necessary but we must not disregard the purpose for the existence of the permits.** As an element of the wish to accelerate Carbon Management technology deployment, many of the stakeholders problematized the length and cost of permitting processes. This has led to calls to streamline these processes. If this is pursued, it must be done in a manner where the purpose of the permits, environmental protection, is still fulfilled.

See the pre-print version of the Määttä et al paper for full details of the study:

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4819526

You can find the European Industrial Carbon Management Communication here:

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2024%3A62%3AFIN>

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